

The Journal is Available at <http://www.ijcada.com>
International Journal of Computer Aided Design and Applications, 2024
Journal Original Website: <http://www.aijournals.org/ijcada>

Variations in Pupillary Response to Virtual Augmented Reality In Real Time

Fatima Isiaka

Department of Computer Science, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

History

Received: 12th, November 2023

Revised: 13th, December 2023

Accepted: 6th, January 2024

Published: 18th, January 2024

Keywords:

Pupil response

Virtual environment

Non-immersive Augmented reality

Optimal response

Mapped fixation coordinate

2D virtual environment

Abstract:

The changes that occur in pupil sizes during a virtual scene are indicative of user engagement and cognitive load for different tasks in an environment such as the Virtual scene. It may also serve as a preferred physiological measure for an applied setting. In scenarios where scene brightness cannot be controlled, the pupil response can be correlated to cognitive-emotional response as leverage in pupil indexing in users. The possibility of predicting the pupillary response of an individual's pupil by factoring out measurement is a major challenge, but this can be modelled through a virtual scene. In this paper, we evaluate the optimal response in pupil response to the virtual scenes through a non-immersive method of augmented reality environment. The result shows error in pupil response is less visible when compared to the visual output in mapped fixation of the XYZ-coordinate and an exponential coordinate of the participant's user-friendly calibration to the virtual scene. This procedure can lead to a pilot study involving training in a 3D environment.

NOTE: The article and abstract is published under the International Journal of Computer Aided Design and Applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Current research [20, 7, 22, 5, 4, 14], has shown that pupil diameter changes are very indicative of user cognition and task engagement. However, it is still not a certain or preferred form of physiological measure [20, 7, 22, 5, 4, 14], for an applied setting. This unacceptance of leveraging the pupil as a form of indexing of users' engagement ranges from the fact that in a scenario where the scenes are bright, the visuals cannot be controlled and the pupil light response confounds the least cognitive-emotional response of the users. If the light response can be predicted, then creating the opportunity that factors out the measurement is a customised process. Some research has evaluated models on pupillary response in 2D and a virtual reality (VR) environment [13, 12, 23, 11, 17]. The results have shown that a linear and exponential model can be the best fit for an individual with an easy-to-use calibration.

The pupil is the most significant attribute in eye movement on an interface for every human-computer interaction (HCI) study. The pupil is the opening of the eye that allows light to reach the retina and iris. This opening changes in size continuously due to factors ranging from pupillary unrest and brightness in changes to sound in both emotional

and cognitive responses. The changes in pupil size are usually measured as pupil diameter changes and it is a useful indicator of user engagement and mental workload. The pupil has been long studied, but its effect on changes in virtual reality environments has yet to be explored. The rapid growth of virtual reality in both hardware and software in recent years has led to an extensive increase in developers, artists, and researchers exploring and creating immersive virtual environments. One of the significant means of augmenting changes in pupil sizes in virtual is through non-immersive augmented reality [19, 2, 9, 16, 18, 8].

Augmented reality is a form of technology that lets users superimpose digital content such as images, text, and sound over a real-world environment. It got a lot of attention in early 2016 [1, 21, 15] when the game interface on Pokemon Go was released, now as time advanced we can interact with such an interface in a superimposed mode in the world through a smartphone screen [10, 3, 6]. Augmented reality (AR) is now becoming part of our everyday life activity, it is practically reality enhanced with interactive digital components. They are mostly found on smartphones and showcase the digitally augmented world. Users can activate a particular smartphone camera and be able to view the real world around them. This method in this paper uses a non-immersive augmented reality as a virtual scene to explore optimal pupil response to the stimuli. The procedure in the method is discussed in the following section.

Figure 1: An experimental setup where participants sit in front of the PC with an embedded webcam to calibrate to the virtual scene.

2 METHOD

The method follows a set of a predefined module, where the initial stage involves thirty participants by setting an experimental study where the users sit in front of a PC with an embedded webcam. Eyes were calibrated to the six corners of the visual field of the PC containing the augmented virtual reality scene. Their pupil response is recorded in sync with their task engagement. The changes in pupil size are computed based on Equation 1, and the optimal response peak in construction is usually correlated with a stressful task.

2.1 Task

The task assigned to each participant in the interaction with a virtual environment that contains natural elements like landscapes, rivers, highlands, and hilltops. The participants are to create and append their virtual characters via digital overlays with subtasks such as:

1. Superimposing real images, text information, and the 3D field

2. Appending real-time directions to characters
3. Annotating and inserting labels
4. Changing the environments with colors that suit the landscape and
5. Altering the user or their environment's appearance through filters and other

applications on the host PC. In understanding what AR is, it's also important to understand what it is not. The task is unlike that of AR and it is not fully immersive, it allows the participants to interact with the physical world through an enhanced virtual scene. Their eye movement and pupil change can be visualised in real-time as engage in their task (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Fixation locations made by eye movement on the predefined virtual task; the fixation points indicate pupil dilation and constriction to the task.

The pupil response measure is modelled as a physiological time-invariant non-linear delay differential first-order equation that defines the changes in pupil area and diameter as a function of the lighting in the surrounding environment which is given as:

$$m(D) = \tanh^{-1} \left(\frac{D-4.9}{3} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dm}{dD} \times \frac{dD}{dt} + 2.30 \tanh^{-1} \left(\frac{D-5}{3} \right) = 5.2 - 0.45 \ln \left(\frac{\varphi[t-\tau]}{4.8 \times 10^{-10}} \right)$$

Where D is the constant change in diameter as measured in millimetres and $\varphi[t-\tau]$ is the luminosity in an intense light that reaches the retina of the eye time t , which can be defined as $\varphi = IA$: the luminance reaching the eye in $lumens/mm^2$. τ is pupil latency, a delay that lies between the point in time where the light pulse touches the retina and begins or rises in the iridal reaction due to nerve transmission, movement, and activation in delay. dm, dD and dt are the derivatives of m function, the pupil diameter at time t . based on research, the pupil constriction in velocity is approximately three times faster than the re-contraction speed. The simulation is obtained using the following step size for the numerical solver, given as:

$$\begin{aligned} dt_c &= \frac{T_c - T_p}{3} \\ dt_d &= \frac{T_c - T_p}{3s} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here, dt_c and dt_d are the derivative dt for both dilation and constriction, which are measured in milliseconds T_c and T_p are the current and previous simulation times in milliseconds. s is a constant parameter that affects the dilation and constricting velocity of the eye movement, this is different for every individual. The section below describes the method adopted model specification and simulation of these concepts.

3 RESULT

Figure 3 shows the aggregate of scatter plots and response in pupil changes in response to color and light from the virtual scene. The mapped fixations are seen to be in synch and correlated to the pupil changes, this indicates the accuracy in response to the virtual field. The result may also indicate that in a non-immersive AR, the pupil diameter will not change relative to the amount of color and visual attention. The pupil dilation also occurs in response to emotional arousal at optimal pupil dilation that goes beyond responding to light. The plot also shows that mapped fixation on the VR scene can evoke negative and positive optimal pupil responses which are related to arousal when they were immersed in the different virtual scenes. One of the procedures is using VR as an emotional trigger since most of the task are complex and requires full concentration.

Figure 3: Aggregate of Scatter plot and response in pupil changes in response to color and light from the virtual scene.

Figure 4 shows the error record in pupil dilation and constriction behaviour in the virtual scene. Using the pupil response, the changes in pupil diameter based on constriction and dilation were recorded, from the baseline, we ran a two-way ANOVA measure, with data generated and found that a significant effect of pupil response change with $F(3.43) = 8.04, p < .001, = .7$. This is a pair-wise comparison with Bonferroni's adjustment that shows normalised pupil changes at every timestamp based on aggregate response. The timestamp at the initial recording has a significantly higher pupil dilation change than all the time intervals. A significant main effect of the condition is pupil dilation change was found in the mapped fixations on the virtual scene and recording during task engagement.

Figure 5 indicates the error recorded in pupil dilation and constriction behaviour to the virtual scene in the mapped fixation on the virtual interface field. The pupil response and the changes in pupil diameter based on constriction and dilation were recorded, and the two-way ANOVA measure found a significant effect of pupil response change with $F(4.45) = 9.04, p < .001, = .8$. This is also a pair-wise comparison with Bonferroni's adjustment as compared to the result above and that shows normalised pupil changes at every timestamp based on aggregate response. Every timestamp at the initial recording has a significantly higher pupil dilation change than all the time intervals.

Figure 4: Significant pupil response at the initial stage of pupil dilation.

Figure 5: : A significant pupil dilation and constriction each time stamp on the mapped fixation on the virtual interface field.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper seeks to investigate the optimal pupillary response to virtual scene through non-immersive augmented reality (AR) experience, the possibility of predicting the pupillary response of an individual's pupil through factor out of the measurement is a major challenge, but this can be modelling through the virtual scene. The paper evaluates the optimal response in pupil response to the virtual scene through a non-immerse method of augmented reality environment. The result shows error in the pupil response is less visible when compared to the visual output in mapped fixation of the XYZ-coordinate and a fractional coordinate of the participant's user-friendly calibration to the virtual scene. This procedure can lead to the pilot study involving training in a 3D environment where the future aim is to base the augmented reality in a 3D enhanced context with 3D-enabled visual glasses. This can enhance user experience and give another perspective to immersive AR.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The author would wish to thank Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria, for their sponsor of this paper.

References

- [1] Aggarwal, R. and Singhal, A. (2019). Augmented reality and its effect on our life. In *2019 9th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence)*, pages 510–515. IEEE.
- [2] AlGerafi, M. A., Zhou, Y., Oubibi, M., and Wijaya, T. T. (2023). Unlocking the potential: A comprehensive evaluation of augmented reality and virtual reality in education. *Electronics*, 12(18):3953.
- [3] Ballagas, R., Borchers, J., Rohs, M., and Sheridan, J. G. (2006). The smartphone: a ubiquitous input device. *IEEE pervasive computing*, 5(1):70–77.
- [4] Belorustceva, K. (2018). Measuring cognitive state from physiological signals in user interface research.
- [5] Eckstein, M. K., Guerra-Carrillo, B., Singley, A. T. M., and Bunge, S. A. (2017). Beyond eye gaze: What else can eyetracking reveal about cognition and cognitive development? *Developmental cognitive neuroscience*, 25:69–91.
- [6] Farman, J. (2020). *Mobile interface theory: Embodied space and locative media*. Routledge.
- [7] Fehringer, B. C. (2021). Optimizing the usage of pupillary based indicators for cognitive workload. *Journal of Eye Movement Research*, 14(2).
- [8] Hensen, B. (2023). A systematic literature review of mixed reality learning approaches. In *International Conference on Extended Reality*, pages 15–34. Springer.
- [9] Hiran, K. K., Doshi, R., and Patel, M. (2024). *Applications of Virtual and Augmented Reality for Health and Wellbeing*. IGI Global.
- [10] Hooper, S. and Berkman, E. (2011). *Designing mobile interfaces: Patterns for interaction design*. " O'Reilly Media, Inc."
- [11] John, B. (2019). Pupil diameter as a measure of emotion and sickness in vr. In *Proceedings of the 11th ACM Symposium on Eye Tracking Research & Applications*, pages 1–3.
- [12] John, B., Raiturkar, P., Banerjee, A., and Jain, E. (2018a). An evaluation of pupillary light response models for 2d screens and virtual reality hmds. In *Proceedings of the ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology (VRST)*. New York, NY: ACM.
- [13] John, B., Raiturkar, P., Banerjee, A., and Jain, E. (2018b). An evaluation of pupillary light response models for 2d screens and vr hmds. In *Proceedings of the 24th ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology*, pages 1–11.
- [14] Lalmas, M., O'Brien, H., and Yom-Tov, E. (2022). *Measuring user engagement*. Springer Nature.
- [15] Langlotz, T., Nguyen, T., Schmalstieg, D., and Grasset, R. (2014). Next-generation augmented reality browsers: rich, seamless, and adaptive. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 102(2):155–169.

- [16] Paulauskas, L., Paulauskas, A., Blavzauskas, T., Damasevicius, R., and Maskeliunas, R. (2023). Reconstruction of industrial and historical heritage for cultural enrichment using virtual and augmented reality. *Technologies*, 11(2):36.
- [17] Qian, K., Arichi, T., Price, A., Dall’Orso, S., Eden, J., Noh, Y., Rhode, K., Burdet, E., Neil, M., Edwards, A. D., et al. (2021). An eye tracking based virtual reality system for use inside magnetic resonance imaging systems. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1):16301.
- [18] Radhakrishnan, U., Koumaditis, K., and Chinello, F. (2021). A systematic review of immersive virtual reality for industrial skills training. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 40(12):1310–1339.
- [19] Schafer, D. and Kaufman, D. (2018). Augmenting reality with intelligent interfaces. *Artificial intelligence: Emerging trends and applications*, 221.
- [20] Szafr, D. and Mutlu, B. (2012). Pay attention! designing adaptive agents that monitor and improve user engagement. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on human factors in computing systems*, pages 11–20.
- [21] Turner, C. (2022). Augmented reality, augmented epistemology, and the real-world web. *Philosophy & Technology*, 35(1):19.
- [22] van der Wel, P. and Van Steenbergen, H. (2018). Pupil dilation as an index of effort in cognitive control tasks: A review. *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, 25:2005–2015.
- [23] Zheng, L. J., Mountstephens, J., and Teo, J. (2020). Four-class emotion classification in virtual reality using pupillometry. *Journal of Big Data*, 7:1–9.